

FEMALE SLAVERY IN THIRTEENTH CENTURY GUJARAT DOCUMENTS IN THE *LEKHAPADDHATI*

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The *Lekhapaddhati*,¹ a collection of model documents prepared around the sixteenth or seventeenth century, is well-known to historians of early medieval India as a repository of the important documents of pre-Sultanate Gujarat. Besides providing valuable evidence for administrative history, the *Lekhapaddhati* documents shed light on the various aspects of social life. Important in this connection are the four documents relating to slavery, dated v.s. 1288/A.D. 1230-31. A.K. Majumdar and Lallanji Gopal have already commented on their general significance.² An annotated literal translation of these documents has been attempted in this paper for the first time.

All these four documents record the sale of female slaves. The absence of any document dealing with male slaves can be understood in the light of the observation made in the *Bṛhaspati Smṛti* that a female slave "could never be acquired and possessed without a written deed (title)".³ This implies that written deeds were not invariably required in the case of male slaves. That male slaves existed is shown in another document in the *Lekhapaddhati*.⁴

Women captured during war were sold as slaves. Once a girl was brought under the fold of slavery, she suffered a total break with her family including her husband. The documents show that relatives of the slave girl from either the father's or the husband's side (should she have married) could not claim her or even disturb her in any way while she was working as a slave. The slave was the exclusive property of the owner (purchaser), who was called a *janmagrāhaka* in recognition of his right to even her life.

One document shows a *rājaputra* girl turned into a slave in the house of a merchant. In the early medieval period, *rājaputras* were members of ruling families and warrior chiefs.⁵ In the *Lekhapaddhati* itself the *rājaputra* appears to be a horseman, controlling

1 *Lekhapaddhati*, ed, C.D. Dalal and G.K. Shrigondekar (Gaekwad Oriental Series, Vol. XIX, Baroda, 1925), pp. 44-47. The *Lekhapaddhati* is henceforth cited in the notes as *LP*.

2 A. K. Majumdar, *Chaulukyas of Gujarat* (Bombay, 1956), pp. 345-49; Lallanji Gopal, *The Economic Life of Northern India c. A.D. 700-1200*, 2nd edn (Delhi, 1989), pp. 71-80.

3 *Bṛhaspati Smṛti*, tr., J. Jolly, *The Sacred Book of the East*, Vol. XXXIII, reprint (Delhi, 1969), p. 312.

4 A smaller document in *LP* dated v.s. 1288 records the division of a dead father's property between two sons. The property inherited includes both *dāsa* and *dāsī* (male and female slaves), *LP*, p. 49.

5 B.N.S. Yadava, *Society and Culture in Northern India in the Twelfth Century* (Allahabad, 1973), pp. 32-33. The literal meaning of the word *rājaputra* is prince and is used as the title of a prince or a subordinate ruler. It subsequently appeared as a title of the nobility, especially in the Prakritized

a village on behalf of the ruler.⁶ In the present case, the girl's family suffered grievously in a famine and had as a result disintegrated as a unit. She, therefore, could hardly have belonged to a chief's family. Even so, it is peculiar that a *rājaputra* girl became a slave to a master belonging to the *vaiśya varṇa*. Yājñavalkya and Nārada prescribe that the master of the slave should be of a higher *varṇa*: a *kṣatriya* could not, therefore, theoretically be a slave of a *vaiśya* or a *śūdra*. Only an apostate from asceticism could be the slave of a *vaiśya* or a *śūdra*.⁷ Obviously, in actual life the *Smṛtis* were not being strictly followed in all details.

The *Lekhapaddhati* documents specify the kinds of work a female slave had to do in her master's house. These duties may be classified into household work and field work. Under the first category are included cutting, grinding, smearing the floor with cowdung, sweeping, fetching water and the fuel, throwing away the excreta of the master's family, milking cattle, churning curd, cooking, cleaning the drains and water tanks of the house, washing the hands and feet of the master and his family, bringing grass for fodder, weeding and cutting grass. Field work included agricultural work, ploughing, threshing, going to near and distant places and doing other unspecified work.

The difference between the duties assigned to an ordinary servant (*bhṛtaka*) and a slave (*dāsa*) was recognized by law. The *Dharmaśāstra* texts show that the former performed "pure" work only, while the latter could also be called upon to do "impure" work.⁸ Our documents show that a slave girl could be asked to do both. Indeed, as Lallanji Gopal has pointed out, the simultaneous employment of a slave girl in both "pure" work (like cooking) and "impure" work (like handling night-soil) is remarkable in that food was not thought to be polluted when touched by hands that had been involved in professionally "impure" tasks.⁹

A slave girl had to perform her duties without complaint. In case of refusal or violation of the master's orders, she was subjected to severe corporal punishment which might sometimes cause her death. The documents contain specific provisions that in such cases no sin was attached to the master and it could be presumed that he had had a purificatory bath in the *Gaṅgā*.

Besides being sold, a slave girl could also be mortgaged by the owner in order to obtain money from his creditor (*dhanika*). The documents show that, at times, slave girls were sent to another family or other places to work, in return for which their masters earned money. Similarly, slaves were sold for cash, kind and sometimes against a gift in order to earn more income. This suggests that the slave was a mere piece of chattel, to be used by the master for service or income as it suited his purpose.

forms of *rāvata*, *rauta*, D.C. Sircar, *Indian Epigraphical Glossary* (Delhi, 1966), pp. 272, 279-80; R.S. Sharma, *Indian Feudalism: c. 300-1200* (Calcutta, 1965), p. 193.

6 LP, pp. 7, 8, 10, 13.

7 P.V. Kane, *History of Dharmaśāstra*, Vol. II, Pt I (Poona, 1941), pp. 185-86.

8 Ibid., p. 185.

9 Lallanji Gopal, op. cit., p. 79, fn. 1.

TRANSLATION

Dāst-Patra Vidhi (Deed of Female Slave)

1

In the Saṃvat year 1288, Vaiśākha Śudi 15, Thursday, today, here, after mentioning the proper line of kings, a deed of sale of a female slave is being written in the following manner. Rāṇā Pratāpa Singh made an attack on another country and brought a fair-looking sixteen-year old girl named Panuṭī as a female slave; after having informed the *pañcamukhanagara*,¹⁰ she was sold at the crossing of the four roads,¹¹ with a blade of grass on her head. The merchant Āsadhara paid as price five hundred and four *Viśalapriya drammas*¹² to Rāṇā Pratāpa Singh and obtained the female slave named Panuṭī for the work of a female slave and proclaimed the fact to all the residents of the town belonging to the four *varṇas*. Henceforth the female slave should honestly perform the [following] duties in the house of the merchant: cutting, grinding, smearing the floor, sweeping, bringing firewood, carrying water, etc., throwing away human excreta, milking the cow, buffalo and goat, churning the curd and carrying butter-milk to the field, and field work such as bringing the fodder, weeding, cutting grass, etc. The merchant should provide unasked food, clothing, and so on, according to the prevailing customs of the land and his wealth to the female slave acquired in the above manner. While the slave girl works in the merchant's house, if her father, brother or husband comes to reclaim her with money¹³ or interrupts (the performance of) her duty, the merchant is entitled to bind, beat or strike her cruelly and send her back to the work of the slave girl as mentioned in the deed. If ever the female slave, being tortured, commits suicide by throwing herself into a well, etc., she would become a she-ass, bitch or Caṇḍālī and die. The merchant should be deemed to be as pure as if he has performed the purificatory bath in the Gaṅgā (*vyavahārakasya gaṅgāsnānam*).¹⁴

10 *Pañcamukhanagara* means the five leading men of the town, according to D. C. Sircar, op. cit., p. 231. But according to the inscription of Sāraṅgadeva (dated v.s. 1348), *pañcamukhanagara* was composed of (a) the *pañca*; (b) the brāhmaṇas who are called *purohitas* here; (c) the *mahājanas*, of whom some were *sādhu (sāhukār)*, *śreṣṭhī (seṭh)*, *ṭhakkura soni (goldsmiths)*, *kaṃsāra (brazier)*, and so forth; (d) *vaṇijyārakas (vanjārās)*; and (e) *nauvittakas (ship-owners)*, *Indian Antiquary*, Vol. XLI, 1912, p. 20. It seems that *pañcamukhanagara* was a body composed of representatives of different professions of the city.

11 *Catuṣpatha* means where four roads meet. It seems that it was a place for the sale of slaves so that the sale might be known to everybody.

12 In epigraphic records there are references to *viśalapri dra*, *viśalapriya drama*, *viśa dra* and *viśalapuri dra*, Lallaṅgi Gopal, op. cit., p. 197. These coins were current in areas which recognized the overlordship of the Caulukyās of Gujarat and may be presumed to have been issued by the Vāghela ruler Viśaladeva (A. D. 1244-64), see Dasharatha Sharma, *Early Chauhan Dynasties* (Delhi, 1959), pp. 302-3.

13 The phrase *dhanikatvaṃ vidhāya* means that the family members of the female slave "by virtue of their wealth" interrupt her in the performance of duty, Dalal, the editor of *LP*, has taken this word to mean "claiming ownership".

14 According to Dalal, these words mean that the purchaser has not incurred any sin thereby, *LP*, p. 119.

To execute the above written conditions, the *rakṣapālas* and residents of the town have been chosen as witnesses. For this purpose Rāṇā Pratāpa Singh and four *rakṣapālas* signed (this document) under their names by their hands. On the request of both the parties, the *pārayijayata* wrote this deed. Omission and addition of any letters should be treated as valid.

II

In the Samvat year 1288, Vaiśākha Śudi 15, Monday, here, today, at Aṇahillapātaka, after mentioning the proper line of kings, a deed of the sale of a female slave is being written at Bālūā village thus. The creditor (*dhanika*) by name Śreṣṭhi Khetāka, resident of this place, employed his money for profit. Now the borrower (*hastāddhārāṇika*) is known by name (name should be mentioned). At the time of the war waged by *mahāmaṇḍalesvara* Rāṇaka Śrī Viradhavaladeva,¹⁵ a *rājaputra* so and so, resident of this place, who made an attack on Maharashtra¹⁶ and brought a fair-looking sixteen-year old girl (who), rich in qualities and beautiful, was sold. The price of the female slave is 60 *drammas*. From now onward, the female slave with her good behaviour and mild nature should perform the duties of cutting, grinding, smearing the floor, cooking, etc., and field work, threshing, etc., and all other kinds of work in the house of the moneylender. If she is sold or given away as a gift to some other person, she should perform the duties without any mischievous intent. If she commits theft or any other misconduct in the house of the moneylender, she should be punished by beating. If being beaten, the slave girl commits suicide by throwing herself into a well or pond, then she will die at an improper place like a she-ass or Caṇḍāli. The innocent blameless moneylender should be deemed to be as pure as if he has performed the purificatory bath in the Gaṅgā. This one who commits suicide does so because of her own fault. While the slave girl is working in the moneylender's house, neither the borrower, her brother, son or relative, nor her paramour should interrupt her work by calling her with signs of the eyes or eyebrows, nor should they disturb her mind. Neither the borrower nor the moneylender should behave with a crooked mind in any respect. To execute the above written conditions and to see that the slave girl performs all the duties and to reimburse any loss (caused by the slave girl) the brother of *rājaputra* so and so has been appointed surety and an oath has been taken at the temple of Śrī Vaidyanātha (Śiva). Here signatures, here witnesses. The deed is being written in this way.

15 Rāṇaka Viradhavaladeva was the son of *mahāmaṇḍalesvara* Rāṇaka Lāvānyaprasāda, the founder of the Vāghela dynasty, H.C. Ray, *The Dynastic History of Northern India (Early Medieval Period)* (New Delhi, 1973), Vol. II, p. 1027; A.K. Majumdar, op. cit., p. 139.

16 It seems that when Rāṇaka Lāvānyaprasāda made a treaty with Rājā Siṃhaṇa, the Yādava ruler in v.s. 1288/A.D. 1230-31 (see *Yamala Patra, LP*, p. 52), Rāṇaka Viradhavala raided Maharashtra and captured some slave girls, one of whom was now being sold.

Svayamāgata-Dāsi Patra Vidhi (Deed of Voluntary Female Slave)

III

In the Saṃvat year 1288, Vaiśākha Śudi 15, Monday, after mentioning the proper line of kings, a deed of (sale of) a female slave, who herself became a female slave, is being written thus. Now a girl of ten years, named Saṃpūrī, a *rājaputri*,¹⁷ daughter of Jagaḍa, has arrived from Sirnāra, a village on the bank of the river Mahī¹⁸ in the east, much harassed by famine and the *mlecchas*, while all the territory was plundered by the Rāṣṭra(kūṭas) (?),¹⁹ abandoned by all the citizens and the entire family; (even her) mother, father, brother, nephew and uncle, etc., all from the family of her father's side, and mother-in-law, father-in-law, husband, husband's elder and younger brothers, all from the family of her husband's side, did not prevent her. Knowing that both the families—father's and husband's—had, due to famine, started begging, she left (her) place in great distress alone. She begged for only a mouthful of grain at every house in every village and then found it impossible to satisfy her hunger even with this. She became extremely emaciated due to want of food and (wore) dirty and ragged clothes. She passed her nights in temples, monasteries, places where water is distributed to travellers (*prapā*), alms-houses and other places, with unkempt hair, looking in all directions and living like a refugee and quite changed due to hunger and thirst, and reflecting over "What to do, where to go, where to stay, and who would be the owner of an orphan like me, the only refuge being death"; speaking in each house, "Lord! I am an orphan, will you keep me as a slave"? Wandering in this manner, by the grace of God, one day of the month in the year so and so the female slave, falling at the feet of the merchant Cāhaḍa, resident of a certain village, said with folded hands: "I have come voluntarily. Please engage me for the work of a female slave and save me from this terrible famine. I shall work according to your order and, as long as I live, work as a female slave and shall perform the duties of cutting, grinding, sweeping, fetching drinking water, smearing the floor with cowdung, throwing away human excreta (and) all other household duties, and (engage in) outside work (such as) cultivation, other field work, etc., zealously perform all these tasks during three seasons, rainy, winter and summer, throughout the day and night, untiringly and without giving any reply. You have to give me food, clothing and foot-wear only, according to your capacity. What more shall I ask for"? When she declared this at the crossroads, the merchant Cāhaḍa accepted her statement and employed her as a slave in the presence of (in the knowledge of) the entire population consisting of the four *varṇas*. Then she made the following statement (took the following oath) regarding her

17 Here the word *rājaputri* means a "rajput woman", not a princess, as mentioned by A.K. Majumdar, op. cit., p. 345.

18 The river Mahirises in Malwa and flows through Gujarat. Near its mouth Andhaka, a *daitya*, was believed to have been killed by Śiva in a cavern.

19 The word *rāṣṭra* here is used for the Rāṣṭrakūṭas, not in the sense of a territorial division. The terms *maṇḍala* and *deśa* are employed for the largest territorial divisions in Gujarat, A.K. Majumdar, op. cit., p. 208.

self-surrender (as a slave) to the merchant Cāhaḍa in the presence of the whole town, "If I, so long as I live, while employed as a slave in your house or in any other house, commit theft, seeing a vacant room with nobody there appropriate some article lying there, or finding that begging has become easier go elsewhere, or in my youth, being tempted or enticed by some man, leave you, or mix with your enemies and do or cause to cheat, conspire, etc., then on the basis of the deed, you will catch me by my hair, bind and beat me, and again put me to the work of a female slave. I shall always throughout the day and night carry out the orders of all the members of your family. If I, (feeling) self-satisfied (*paripūrṇā*), out of mischievous intent, refuse to perform the duties when ordered to do so, you will punish me by kicking and beating me with sticks and torture me to death, for which you, my Lord, will be as free from guilt, as had you been absent. I declare this in the presence of the four *varṇas* that I will die by my own fault. You, my Lord, with (your) son, grandson, wife and other family members shall be absolved as if by bathing in the Gaṅgā. If I ever feign stomach ache (*udarabādhā*) or commit suicide by jumping into a well or pond or by taking poison, the *pañcamukhanagara* should know that you, my Lord, are guiltless, and that I have died in consequence of my own previous actions and due to fate. My Lord with his family members should be deemed to be as pure as if he has performed the purificatory bath in the Gaṅgā". In this way, in the knowledge of the *pañcamukhanagara* and in the knowledge of the *pañcakula* consisting of *mahājana* and *brāhmaṇa* so and so, the document is signed by my own hand with a sign of *svastika*. Five witnesses.

IV

The preamble (beginnings) and date, etc., as before. (Arrived) from a certain place, daughter of so and so, motivated by her own actions, known by the name so and so, 12-year old, having fair complexion, long ears, whose husband died, having lost her relatives on both sides such as father, mother, father-in-law, husband's elder and younger brothers, became an orphan, having black eyes, pointed nose, unkempt hair, neither short nor tall, with all her limbs in proper form and with these qualities, she is standing in person. Therefore, this female slave, from this very day, till the end of her life, should perform duties in the house of a certain purchaser and by his order in the houses of others and other families, such as cutting, grinding, cooking, sweeping, smearing the floor, fetching water, ploughing, washing hands and feet, cleaning the gutter (*khāla*) and reservoirs of water (*kuṇḍika*), tending cattle and going to places far and near, and all other household work, field work, work on the threshing floor, etc., and all other kinds of work throughout the day and night, during winter and summer, even in hunger and thirst. This female slave, who has been purchased by paying full price, can be mortgaged, or she can be given away in charity. With the desire to earn a little or more money, she can be sent to another country, she can be put in a boat (*pravaḥana*)²⁰ and sent to another island and sold for cash, kind or against gifts. Whatever is liked and contemplated by the Lord, that is to be done. The seller had bought her

20 The literal meaning of this word is a vehicle or any large carrier like a boat or ship. See Apte, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, s. v.; Sircar, op. cit., pp. 262, 358.

at the time of her birth and she is his sole property; now she is being sold to the (purchaser) as a slave.²¹ Due to bad conduct or youth, being tempted by someone out of a desire for money or out of love towards the father, mother, brother and other relatives, if she disappears from the house of the purchaser so and so, according to the deed held in hand, or under royal order he will punish her by kicking and will catch her by the hair, bind and beat her and employ her again for the work of a female slave. Now these are the several duties of the female slave. . . . From this day onwards, the purchaser, his sons, grandsons, etc., shall be the masters of this female slave. From this very day till death, the father, brother, uncle and other relatives belonging to a certain purchaser should not be liable to pay any extra money to the seller (*lāgabhāgonahi*),²² either in cash or kind. Children and old persons are not connected (with this).

21 The term *janmagrāhaka* refers here to the right of the purchaser to the life of the slave.

22 The literal meaning of the term *lāgabhāga* is "payment in kind", Sircar, op. cit., p. 48.